

Letters 1916-1923 is an extension of Letters of 1916: Ireland's first participatory engagement digital humanities project. The archive is co-created with the public, from over 60 families depositing digital copies of their private collections into the archive, to the over 2000 people registered to transcribe letters in our system. At the same time, the project team has sourced collections from some 30 institutions across Ireland, the UK (Belfast, Liverpool and Manchester) and the US (Chicago and New York). Since the project's launch in September 2013, over 5000 letters have been collected. New collections reflect the expansion of the project through 1923 and cover topics such as the end of The Great War (1917-1918), voting rights for women, the Anglo-Irish War and the Irish Civil War. The latter events, especially the Civil War, are still politically sensitive. Hence the ways in which we handle the sensitivities that the expanded collecting period brings takes into account the multifaceted collaborations and interests of academics, archivists, teachers, students and individual members of the public

The strength and challenge of the project is its evolutionary development: no pre-defined corpus, and funding from multiple sources for limited periods of time and for specific aspects of the project. Because of its organic development, the first phase of the project utilised three separate databases: "Learn" was a blog for project information (eg information on the project, its team, contextual blog posts by team members and members of the public, information on public engagement events, and project news); "Contribute", an Omeka installation that facilitated public involvement in adding new letters and transcribing previously uploaded letters; and "Explore" which integrated metadata, images, and transcription into a seamless reading, searching, and browsing environment.

While the Letters 1916-1923 corpus cannot be considered big data, it nevertheless, is significantly larger than most one-off editing projects. It may be more aptly termed a project of the middle distance in its diversity, richness, and organic collection processes. The liminal nature of the collection informed its technical redevelopment through a grant from the Irish Research Council beginning in 2017. The redesigned architecture features one database to facilitate all the functions above, as well as a seamless workflow between the various components. This paper will explore how data analytics was used to not only to generate research output, but also to substantiate each step of data collection and data management. It will also explore the redesign of the data model and the redevelopment of the system architecture.

In order to facilitate infrastructural improvements, data analytics were used to find problems which could potentially break the transcription and publication systems, or which hindered content interpretation. Analytics were used for data cleaning and script-based validation to reduce human intervention in the transcription, proofing and publication phases in favour of script-based data validation. A key part of the cleaning process was to identify different spellings of named entities (people, places, organisations, and events). This involved correcting typos that had crept into the data entry process, matching Irish and English spellings of names for the same individual and/or matching different spellings within English or Irish, and identifying full names from initials where possible. This allowed for the construction of a social network, as in Figure 1.

Letter Network

Fig 1. An undirected network map of some of the correspondents with the largest networks

Interestingly, the social network generated, despite the corpus's limited and constrained time frame, has a low average path length (six degrees of separation), a property commonly found in large social networks (Newman 2003). Although the data in the Letters 1916-1923 database come from collections which are vastly different in size, ranging from individual letters deposited by families to sets of hundreds of letters provided by libraries and archives, the network analysis confirmed established theories that connections between database items approximate a mean path length of 6 as the amount of available data increases. This network theory has been tested for database items as diverse as the neural network of the nematode worm, the US Power Grid, and even movie actors ('Kevin Bacon Game'), a property known as "small world" (Watts & Strogatz, 1998). In our case, the mean path length turned out to be 6.01, with a maximum path length of 17.

The transcription of the text of each letter also allowed us to identify further connections between people increasing the density of the network. Key players in the network were also identified. Geocoding place names allowed for a network analysis plotted spatially, as in Figure 2:

The Letters Project 1916-23

Figure 2: Letters plotted on a world map

In terms of the architecture redesign, the goal was to unify the technologies involved to create a scalable and reproducible software environment for the infrastructure redeployment and data exchange. The team adopted an agile programming approach (Atlassian) with the following objectives:

- Provide documentation and make the platform environment agnostic;
- Document and build a sustainable deployment process;
- Introduce new features to the existing deployment;
- Test the deployment process;
- Update the data model for a scalable infrastructure;
- Design and develop a new platform for data exchange and publishing (called Magellan);
- Design and develop a data ingestion API on the new platform;
- Define a new information workflow;
- Integrate the old transcription platform with the new platform via the API.

An updated data model was developed, the result of a collaboration between the technical and the content teams. The updated data model contains all necessary elements of a letter, a short description of every element, special validation criteria, the format and the cardinality of an element. While each letter was previously expressed only in XML/TEI, the new architecture includes a redesigned data model, i.e. the mapping of existing XML/TEI files to JSON in order to improve the publication process of transcribed texts, and updated tagging / categories used to display letters on the browse page as in Figure 3.

Figure 3: the redesigned browse page.

The stable release of the data model enabled the development of the core of the new system, the Magellan API (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Existing and updated infrastructure

The flexible and extensible nature of the API enables the integration and consumption of data with different formats and the use of different database and data storage solutions. Currently supported data sources include data from Omeka, data in XML/TEI format and data from the new transcription desk, but the API can easily adapt to future incoming data formats. Batch processes are implemented to allow for the automatic build of the database from a set of XML/TEI documents. This API also allowed the redevelopment of the client-side interface, for both the transcription desk and the final letters display environment.

Similarly, the new transcription desk has been redesigned based on feedback from transcribers, especially at outreach events, as well as observation by team members. The current transcription environment is out of the box DIY History, an Omeka plugin, with the addition of a transcription toolbar (developed by the Transcribe Bentham project). While on the one hand, the project was committed to exposing the transcriber community to some of the technologies normally hidden from view, in our case the XML tags, and providing them with an interface to participate in the tagging process (Figure 5), on the other hand, the highly irregular and idiosyncratic encoding by the public placed a huge burden on the project team who had to correct it by hand. Thus a more simplistic/failsafe approach was introduced in the developed of the new transcription desk (Figure 6) which not only hid the tagging process from the end-user, but allowed for text encoding and saving on the fly.

Powered by BrainMaps API

If a larger sized image is not displaying [click here](#) to activate an alternative viewer.

This item is editable! [Sign in](#) or [register](#) to track your edits, watch pages, etc.

← | pbA | P | + | str | ? | [...] | 🗨 | U | x² | :SIC | fr | & | - | <- | S | D

```
<address>Cashelagor  
</address>  
<address>Gortahork</address>  
<date>15 - 12 - 22</date>  
<salute>A Cara</salute>  
<p>I got your letter on the 13th,  
</p>  
<p>and am glad to hear all you boys  
</p>  
<p>are well. A funny thing about your  
</p>
```

Save edits

prev | next | all images | history | transcription instructions

Figure 5: a screenshot of the current transcription desk

Transcribe Letter

Figure 6: a screenshot of the new transcription desk

This presentation will explore the new architecture of the Letters of 1916-1923 project, lessons learned in its development and redevelopment, which should be of interest to other participatory or crowd-sourced digital humanities projects.

Bibliography

Atlassian: The Agile Coach. Atlassian's no-nonsense guide to agile development: <https://www.atlassian.com/agile>

Bellini, Pierfrancesco, et al. "Metrics for Best Practice Networks Analysis." DISIT-DSI, Distributed Systems and Internet Technology Lab, doi:<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/e78e/1ef8b387c8fa8e688bb687bb97ee76531518.pdf>.

Comsa, Maria, et al. "Voltaire and the Enlightenment." Mapping The Republic of Letters, Stanford University, republicofletters.stanford.edu/casestudies/voltaire.html. Accessed on 12 March 2018.

Guns, Raf, et al. "Q-Measures and Betweenness Centrality in a Collaboration Network: a Case Study of the Field of Informetrics." SpringerLink, Springer, Dordrecht, 1 Jan. 2011, link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11192-010-0332-3.

Letters 1916-1923: 1916 Letters Topic Modeling Project: <https://github.com/bleierr/1916Letters>

Letters 1916-1923: Re-design of the Letters 1916-1923 project website, 2017-2018:
<https://github.com/Maynooth-Center-for-Digital-Humanities>

Newman, Mark EJ. "The structure and function of complex networks." *SIAM review* 45.2 (2003): 167-256.

Newman, Mark EJ, and Juyong Park. "Why social networks are different from other types of networks." *Physical Review E* 68.3 (2003): 036122.

Watts, Duncan J., and Steven H. Strogatz. "Collective dynamics of 'small-world' networks." *nature* 393.6684 (1998): 440.

Weingart, S. "Demystifying Networks" (2011). <http://journalofdigitalhumanities.org/1-1/demystifying-networks-by-scott-weingart/>

Kent Beck, Mike Beedle, Arie van Bennekum, Alistair Cockburn, Ward Cunningham, Martin Fowler, James Grenning, Jim Highsmith, Andrew Hunt, Ron Jeffries, Jon Kern, Brian Marick, Robert C. Martin, Steve Mellor, Ken Schwaber, Jeff Sutherland, Dave Thomas: Manifesto for Agile Software Development, 2001: <http://agilemanifesto.org/>